

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE E Season NS 80

Area: EST Square ^{N11}E9-10 Locus Number (1)

Progress of Excavation 22/VI/80 - SQUARE SURVEYED, LAID OUT // 23/VI/80

Elevations taken corners, center, Photographed RW & COLOR OF SURFACE
CLEARING begins w/ fas men taking of ~10 cms loose soft sand w/ mud
inclusions. This called (1) LOOSE SAND. Underneath a hard packed sand.
Zahi tells his assistants (Ismail) this packed sand is same level. I
tell them to call it (1b). No sifting. Pottery to be collected in
baskets

Locus Description LOOSE SAND

Location in Square Across Square

Under Locus SURFACE Over Locus (1b) Packed sand

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels Corners: NE 10.00, SE 9.54, SW 8.89, SF 9.07, CENTER 9.29

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____